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Summary

As one of several R & D projects of Composites in Japan, the national eight year term project and its progress are introduced. The aim of this project is to create advanced FRP and FRM Composites exceeding the target as shown in Table I and Figure 1 and being applicable to aero-space structures, jet engines and automobiles. The brief progress in past four years is outlined.

Introduction

There are several R & D projects in progress. Among them, since the national project seems to be most systematic, elaborate and representative, its brief introduction is presented here.

In 1981, the Agency of Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) of Ministry of International Trade and Industry has started eight national R & D projects for future industry in Japan. Among them, there was eight year term R & D project on Advanced Composite Materials (ACM). And its steering committee, headed by the author, was organized and the Research and Development Institute of Metals and Composite Materials for Future Industry was established for concrete promotion of the projects.

The aim of this project is to create ACM, being applicable to aerospace structures, jet engines and automobiles. The systematic research and development work on ACM ranging from the basic materials, preforms and processing to design- and evaluation-technology has been continuing since 1981.

The target of this project for FRP and FRM, which was given by AIST, is shown in Table I and Figure 1. Composites, which exceed these targets, would predominate in other materials at present and probably at the end of the project term.

Table I. Target for Advanced Composites

FRP	(1) Heat Resistant Temperature $\geq 250^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2) Tensile Strength* $\geq 2.35 \text{ GPa}$ (240 kgf/mm ²)
FRM	(1) Heat Resistant Temperature $\geq 450^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2) Tensile Strength* $\geq 1.47 \text{ GPa}$ (150 kgf/mm ²)

* Strength by standard specimen and at 90 % retention.

Figure 1 - Target area on specific tensile strength versus temperature diagram.

The project is now being done by team work of one University, 5 National Institutes and 12 Companies.

The present report consists of following four parts:

- Part I : Advanced Plastics for FRP Composites,
II : Fabrication Techniques of FRP Composites,
III : Metal Matrix Composites,
and IV : Design and Evaluation Technology.

Part I. Advanced Plastics for FRP Composites

In R & D of advanced FRP composites, we have two objectives, namely, R & D of high performance plastics and R & D of fabrication techniques of FRP. Here the progress of the first one is stated and the second one in Part II.

Limiting the target to R & D of heat resistant plastics, the increase of heat resistance and anti-hygroscopicity of Epoxy resin, the improvement of processability of Polyimide resin and R & D of new type heat resistant resin are being promoted.

In what follows, the essential parts of results conducted by our team members are introduced (1).

I-1 "Present Studies on New Heat Resistant Epoxy Resins "

by S. Ohashi, Research Center, Mitsubishi Chemical Industry Co., Ltd.

New three types of heat resistant Epoxy resins for high performance Carbon Fiber (CF) / Epoxy composites have been studied: Epoxy resin having (1) highly crosslinked-, (2) hydrophobic- and (3) heat resistant-structures, respectively.

Highly crosslinked Epoxy (PGP), which has 4 functional groups, has shown T_g as high as 270°C and elastic modulus of 3.92 GP_a (400 kgf/mm^2). The other two kinds of Epoxy are being developed.(1).

I-2 "Development of Polyimide Resins "

by Y. Aito, Products Development Research Laboratory, Teijin Ltd.

Polyimides have good thermal stability, but poor fabricability and high cost. In order to eliminate these demerits and improve the fabricability, maintaining its heat resistant property, three approaches were tried: (1) Polyimide resin of controllable terminal group type (TPI),

(2) Polyimide resin of new main chain type (MPI) and

(3) Polyimide resin of new oligomer type (OPI).

Table II shows some result of property of those three type Polyimides developed.(1)

I-3 "Development of Polyphenylquinoxaline Resins"

by N. Odagiri, Pioneering R & D Laboratory, Toray Industries, Inc.

Modified Polyphenylquinoxaline resin (PPQ) were synthesized by copolymerization with tetracarboxylic-dianhydride in order to improve its thermal resistance.

As a result of thermal analysis and IR measurement, it was revealed that the ladder structure was formed in two stages, i.e., imidization at about 120°~ 200°C, pyrrolone ring formation at about 250°~300°C.

Glass transition temperature and 5 % weight loss temperature of modi-

Table II. Property of Polyimide Composites*

Item	Temperature	TPI	MPI	OPI	Target for First Stage
Tensile Strength (GPa)	RT	2.19	1.98	2.33	2.06
	250°C, 10min	1.94	1.82	2.18	1.86
	-60°C, 10min	1.84	2.18	2.18	1.67
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	RT	164	134	153	152
Elongation (%)	RT	1.34	1.38	1.59	1.35
Flexural Strength (GPa)	RT	2.47	2.40	2.38	2.01
	250°C, 10min	1.82	1.70	1.65	1.53
	250°C, 500hr	2.43	1.69	1.34	1.32
ILSS (GPa)	RT	0.113	0.067	0.162	0.0882
V _f (%)	—	69.4	64.4	65.0	65

* : Torayca 400/ Polyimide,

ILSS : Interlaminar shear strength,

V_f : Fiber volume fraction,

1 GPa = 102 kgf/mm².

fied PPQ were higher than those of PPQ homopolymer, showing superior thermal resistance. The mechanical properties of T400/modified PPQ composites were evaluated. Table III shows some result. (1).

Table III. Property of Torayca 400/ PPQ Composite

Item	Temperature	Copolymer PPQ
σ Tensile Strength (GPa)	-60°C	1.63
	RT	1.63
	250°C	1.71
σ Tensile Modulus (GPa)	RT	151
ε Elongation (%)	RT	1.08
σ Flexural Strength (GPa)	RT	1.47
	250°C, 10 min	1.27
	250°C, 500hr	1.32
ILSS (GPa)	RT	0.0882
V _f (%)	—	64.0

Before the fabrication technique for heat resistant plastics composite will be studied, the development of fabrication process of composite integral structures was attempted. Further, integral processing by laminating and molding methods for aircraft structures, low pressure-fast curing process of large panel components for automobiles, continuous processing of thin-walled long structural components for space vehicles, automated fabrication and secondary machining problems have been investigated. Using small size components, the researches for updating of processing technique and enhancing the reliability and productivity have also been conducted.

II-1 " Molding Processes for Integral Structures"

by K. Ojio, Aircraft Engineering Division, Kawasaki Heavy Industry, Ltd.

Two new processes for the fabrication of CFRP integral structures were developed. The first molding process is a deep-drawing technique using preforms braided by filament-winding. This preform fabric is more suitable to lay-up a deep complex shape components than conventional satin fabric. The another developed process is a molding process using short-fiber prepreg uni-directionally oriented and intermeshed by electro-static flocking. By such procedure, the casting of composites is possible, and the lag piece for joint was made by casting of short-fiber oriented composites. (1).

II-2 " Low Pressure, Fast Curing Cycle FRP Fabrication Technique"

by K. Sekiyama , Materials R & D Department, Toyota Motor Corporation.

As a fabrication process of large size FRP component for future automobile, low pressure and fast curing cycle process is required from the need of high productivity. Figure 2 shows the targets for future FRP fast cure fabrication techniques for large size panels.

Figure 2. Processing pressure vs cycle for present and future.

Three fabrication techniques have been developed for better quality and specifically for improved productivity. (1) Hot press molding utilizes carbon fiber SMC, and its fiber and sheet geometries, fiber content and charging patterns were investigated. (2) Stretch forming has inherent advantages in its low cost and low pressure, but requires careful compromise

of resin dispensing, degassing and forming conditions. (3) In resin injection molding, special attentions were paid to establish a system which realizes fast mold filling and curing while suspending a gelation during mold filling. (1).

II-3 " CO₂ Laser Application for CFRP Cutting"
by T.Hasegawa , Fuji Heavy Industries, Ltd.

Mechanical cutting methods for CFRP laminates involve some problem point: the rapid wear of cutter and the pollution caused by CFRP powder during cutting. To eliminate such demerit and to improve productivity, a development study of CO₂ laser cutting technique for CFRP was conducted.

In laser cutting work of composites such as CFRP, AFRP and GFRP whose matrices are Epoxy resin, the size of area degenerated by cutting is greatest in CFRP, followed by GFRP and smallest in AFRP (Aramid Fiber RP), depending on thermal conductivity of fibers. In order to decrease the degenerated area, the increase of laser power (up to 1500 Watt output in single mode) and the suitable selection of good spot diameter and cutting speed for each composites were studied. (1).

II-4 " Process Control Technique of CFRP by Curing Process Monitoring"
by K. Itoh , Kawasaki Heavy Industry, Ltd.

This paper presents the research results for a new process control technique of autoclave cure process for CFRP prepreg. The object of this study was to characterize specific electrical properties during the curing cycle of CFRP prepreg. The electrical properties studied were electric resistance, electric potential of interelectrodes, electric capacitance and dissipation factor of CFRP prepreg.

The results showed several good correlation between curing effects and monitored electric signal and described some availabilities of electrical properties for the process control of CFRP. (1).

Part III. Metal Matrix Composites

In the project of Metal Matrix Composites (MMC), there were two plans: R & D of (1) high performance preform materials and (2) fabrication technique for those materials.

As for the first plan (1), the fabrication of wire preforms of CF and SiCF by infiltration of Aluminum alloy was attempted and those continuous production in laboratory scale was a good success.

In the second plan (2)-R & D of the basic fabrication techniques, (a) press- or roll-forming, using thin film preform made from CF, SiCF and Boron Fiber, on whose surfaces ion-plating, plasma spray or slurry spray of Al-alloy was applied, (b) HIP process of short fibers, (c) infiltration or extrusion when SiC-whiskers were used as reinforcement, and etc. have been conducted. Even small simple form products, they have shown good property of world level.

III-1 " Surface Treatment for Carbon Fibers as Aluminum Reinforcement"
by A. Shindo and K. Honjo, Government Industrial Research
Institute, Osaka.

A CVD method for SiC coating was investigated on PAN-based ungraphitized carbon fibers. The decrease of tensile strength of CF brought about by SiC coating was prevented by coating a free carbon-containing SiC layer as an undercoat.

If a titanium-boron treatment was further applied to CF yarns with the double layers coating and then they were infiltrated with molten Aluminum, they have shown a fairly marked improvement of strength. (1).

III-2 " The Effect of the Interfacial Condition on Strength of CF-Al Composites",

by S. Ohnishi , Pioneering Research and Development Laboratory, Toray Industry, Inc.

The strength of CF-Al UD-Composites fabricated by liquid infiltration process was investigated. Its tensile strength is largely affected by the aluminum carbide formed in the interfacial zone during the liquid infiltration process. It was found that the tensile strength in the fiber direction of UD composite is inversely proportional to the logarithmic value of the amount of aluminum carbide formed in the interface between the fibers and matrix, and it was possible to get the tensile strength 140 kgf/mm^2 (1.37 GP_a) by largely reducing the quantity of aluminum carbide in the interface. CF-wire preform technique for obtaining such high strength was developed. (1).

III-3 " Development of Wire-Preform for SiC Fiber-NICALON-Reinforced Aluminum Composite Materials ",

by Y. Imai, R & D Laboratory, Nippon Carbon Co., Ltd.

Silicon carbide continuous fiber-Nicalon-, produced from polycarbosilane of organosilicon compound, possesses outstanding properties, such as high strength, high modulus, high temperature resistance. Fiber diameter is about $15 \mu\text{m}$ and yarn of 500 filaments is available.

R & D of wire-preform of Nicalon and Al was in progress and the wires are suitable to make metal matrix composites by hot pressing, rolling and etc. At present, ca 100 meter long wire-preform having tensile strength of 100 kgf/mm^2 after the exposure of -200 C for 100 hr and 400 C for 100 hr is available. (1).

III-4 " Fabrication of Carbon or SiC Fiber-Reinforced Metal Composites "

by A. Sakamoto , Nagoya Aircraft Works, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd.

Fabrication process of continuous, multifilament CF and SiCF reinforced Aluminum was investigated. The reaction effect between fibers and aluminum during fabrication process and the mechanical properties were studied.

The solidifying phenomena during hot-pressing of liquid-phase Al-infiltrated preform wires and hot-rolling of Al-plasma-sprayed or ion-plated preform sheets were studied and developed. (1).

III-5 " Fabrication of Metal Matrix Composites Reinforced with CVD Filaments ",

by S. Masaki , Aero-engine and Space Operations Division, Ishikawajima-Harima Heavy Industries Co., Ltd.

R & D of the hot-press process of Boron Fiber (BF) ($0.1 \sim 0.2 \text{ mm}$ diameter) or SiC-Fiber preforms, which were made by CVD (Chemical Vapor Deposition) method, were conducted. (1).

The effect of heat cycle on CVD-SiC interfacial reaction, the effect of fabrication temperature, pressure and fiber volume fraction on SiCF-reinforced Ti-6Al-4V composites, the directional properties of strength of BF/Al and hybridization of Ti-sheet and CF/Al were investigated, and a hybrid of BF/Al and CF/Al were investigated. Among them, it is to be noted that an intra-laminate of BF/Al and CF/Al has shown greater tensile strength 142 kgf/mm^2 (1.4 GP_a) than 108 kgf/mm^2 of BF/Al and 58 kgf/mm^2 of CF/Al

for some configuration of laminate. This is the phenomenon denominated by the author as " hybrid effect " (2).

III-6 " Development Target for Fiber Reinforced Metals "

by H. Kikukawa , Aircraft Engineering Division, Fuji Heavy Industry, Ltd.

FRM have received special attention in the area of aero-space technology, because of excellent potential. In order to give a concrete form to those merits, an analytical approach to the targets of development was attempted. Procedure to analyze the targets is as follows:

(1) Resolution of Structure into Components

A structure can be broken down into basic components. Since the target for structural components: tie, column, plate and cylinder do not depend on any structural configuration, they are usable conveniently.

(2) Procedure to find the Target of Development

a. Selection of Index for Strength and Rigidity of Structural Components.

As index used for comparison of mechanical properties, specific strength (strength/ specific gravity) and specific modulus (modulus/ specific gravity) were used. Structural indices for buckling in Table IV were cited from papers (3) to (5) of the present author.

b. Introduction of Target for Weight Reduction

FRM should surpass the competitive conventional metals: 7075-T6, Ti-6Al-4V, 4340 St for space structure, the above metals plus Al-Lithium alloy for aircraft structure, Ti-6Al-4V, EFR Cmv, 17-22A, INCOLOY 901, INCO 718 for aero-engine materials. And taking into account higher price of FRM, it was assumed that FRM can make 25% reduction of structural weight, and also exceeds advanced FRP in mechanical properties. As mechanical properties of FRP, tensile strength $F_L = 240 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$ and modulus $E_L = 1.4 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$ (Refer to Table I) for aircraft structure and engine, and $F_L = 150 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$, $E_L = 2.4 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$ for space structure were used, and both of above strengths should maintain 90 % of strength at 250°C. And as thermal environment, thermal loadings of $-70^\circ \sim 450^\circ \text{C}$, $-150^\circ \sim 250^\circ \text{C}$ and $-50^\circ \sim 120^\circ \text{C}$ for aircraft, space structure and aero-engine, respectively, were assumed to be imposed.

c. Ply Composition of Laminate taken as Basic Reference Material

For comparison of the structural properties, a model laminate of (0° ply of $V_f=50\%$, $\pm 45^\circ$ ply of $V_f=50\%$) was considered. As the final target values, all of properties were converted into the value of 0° ply of 100% UD laminate. Modulus E of abscissa of Figure 3, 4 and 5 shows such converted values.

(3) Targets obtained

Figure 3, 4 and 5 show plots of results obtained for each thermal environment. In these Figures, the marks \oplus represent the targets for tensile loading for specific strength F/γ and specific modulus E/γ at room temperature (RT), 250°C and 450°C respectively. The marks \boxtimes shows targets for buckling load. The marks \bullet , \blacksquare represent the experimentally obtained data. These results indicate that the experimental results are gradually approaching the targets.

Besides the above analysis, fatigue and cost problems were discussed in this paper.(1).

Table IV. Material and Structural Indices

(a) Material Indices

Item	Component	Material Index
Strength	Tie, Column	$F_L / \gamma, F_T / \gamma$
	Shear Member	F_{LT} / γ
Rigidity		$E_L / \gamma, E_T / \gamma, G / \gamma$

L & T : Principal axes of orthotropy,
 E_L, E_T, G : Elastic moduli referred to principal axes,
 F_L, F_T : Strength in the directions of principal axes,
 F_{LT} : Shear strength in L-T inplane shear,
 γ : Specific gravity.

(b) Structural Indices for Buckling Failure

	Component	Load	Structural Index
Failure by Buckling	Column	Compression	$\sqrt{E_L} / \gamma$
	Plate	Compression	$\left[\frac{\sqrt{E_L E_T} + E_L \nu_T}{1 - \nu_L \nu_T} + 2G \right]^{1/3} / \gamma$
		Shear	$12 \sqrt{E_L E_T^3} / \gamma$
	Cylinder	Compression	$\sqrt{4 E_L E_T} / \gamma$
		Bending	$\sqrt{4 E_L E_T} / \gamma$
		Torsion	$10 \sqrt{E_L E_T^3} / \gamma$
		External pressure	$3 \sqrt{E_T} / \gamma$

L : Principal axis L is parallel to column axis,
 plate edge or cylinder axis,
 T : Principal axis T is perpendicular to axis L,
 ν_L, ν_T : Poisson's ratios referred to L and T axes,
 $E_L / E_T = \nu_L / \nu_T$.

Remark : In the above formulae, it was assumed the materials have the homogeneous orthotropy through the thickness.

Figure 3 - Target of static specific strength F/γ and specific modulus E/γ of FRM, at room temperature, $\gamma = 2.3$

(a) For aircraft structure and aero-engine:

- P_1 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load,
 $F_L = 2.30 \text{ GP}_a$ (235 kgf/mm²)
 $E_L = 98.0 \text{ GP}_a$ (1.00×10^4 kgf/mm²).
- B_1 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of
 column : compression
 plate : compression, shear
 cylinder : compression, bending,
 torsion, external pressure.
 $E_L = 81.3 \text{ GP}_a$ (0.83×10^4 kgf/mm²).

(b) For space structure:

- P_2 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load,
 $F_L = 1.18 \text{ GP}_a$ (121 kgf/mm²),
 $E_L = 131 \text{ GP}_a$ ($1,34 \times 10^4$ kgf/mm²)
- B_2 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of
 cylinder : compression, bending, torsion,
 external pressure,
 $E_L = 139 \text{ GP}_a$ (1.42×10^4 kgf/mm²)
- B_3 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of
 column : compression,
 plate : compression, shear.
 $E_L = 324 \text{ GP}_a$ (3.31×10^4 kgf/mm²)

Figure 4 - Target of static specific strength F/γ and specific modulus E/γ of FRM, at 250°C , $\gamma = 2.3$

(a) For aircraft structure and aer-engine:

P_1 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load,

$F_L = 1.52 \text{ GP}_a$ (155 kgf/mm^2),

$E_L = 100 \text{ GP}_a$ ($1.02 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$),

B_1 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of

column : compression,

plate : compression, shear

cylinder: compression, bending,

torsion, external pressure.

$E_L = 58.8 \text{ GP}_a$ ($6 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$).

(b) For space structure :

P_2 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load,

$F_L = 1.03 \text{ GP}_a$ (105 kgf/mm^2),

$E_L = 152 \text{ GP}_a$ ($1.55 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$).

B_2 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of

cylinder: compression, bending,

torsion, external pressure,

$E_L = 142 \text{ GP}_a$ ($1.45 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$).

B_3 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of

column : compression,

plate : compression, shear,

$E_L = 316 \text{ GP}_a$ ($3.22 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$).

(B_3 is not shown in Figure 4.)

Figure 5 - Target of static specific strength F/γ and specific modulus E/γ of FRM, at 450°C, $\gamma = 2.3$.

(a) For aircraft structure :

P_1 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load,

$$F_L = 1.32 \text{ GP}_a \text{ (} 135 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \text{) ,}$$

$$E_L = 93.1 \text{ GP}_a \text{ (} 9.50 \times 10^3 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \text{) ,}$$

B_1 = Target (E/γ) for buckling load of

column : compression,

plate : compression, shear,

cylinder: compression, bending,

torsion, external pressure.

$$E_L = 53.9 \text{ GP}_a \text{ (} 5.50 \times 10^3 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \text{) .}$$

(b) For aero-engine :

P_2 = Target (F/γ , E/γ) for tensile load of

tie : tension

plate: tension,

$$F_L = 1.18 \text{ GP}_a \text{ (} 120 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \text{) ,}$$

$$E_L = 103 \text{ GP}_a \text{ (} 1.05 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \text{) .}$$

Part IV. Design and Evaluation Technology

The project had two theses: development of design technology and quality evaluation technology. The development of these technologies is indispensable in R & D of new advanced composite materials.

a. Design technology: Actively using the directional properties of FRP and FRM, the suppression of detrimental deformation of structure, the decrease of air drag of wing, optimum design of wing structure, the structural index for FRP and FRM structure and so on have been investigated.

b. Quality evaluation technology: Various inspection technology of defects in composite materials and structures, evaluation technology of environmental resistivity and degradation, process control, process monitoring technique and etc. have been studied.

In this part IV, 4 reports are introduced.

IV-1 " Tailored Design Studies of Composite Structures"

by T. Ugai , Aircraft Engineering Division, Fuji Heavy Industry, Ltd.

For the design of tailored wing structure, the use of computer program is indispensable. A computer program called COSMOS (Composite Structure Multi-constraint Optimization System) has been developed since 1981, and used for several optimization problems in past.

Present COSMOS enables to optimize a composite laminate under three constraints for strength, deflection and flutter speed. This was applied to designs of a swept plate wing and a box wing, and those analysis was compared with test results in good agreement. (1).

IV-2 " Evaluation of Stiffness and Strength of CFRP for Space Application", by K. Tsukui , Central Research Laboratory, Mitsubishi Electric Corp.

Experimental and analytical investigations were conducted to evaluate the stiffness and strength of CFRP laminates and thin-walled pipes with several kinds of stacking sequences which were designed as components of a space structure and made by filament-winding process. The analytical results of deflection and strength have shown good agreement with test results. (1).

IV-3 " Degradation Characteristics of CFRP by Heat and Humidity Cycles and Thermal Shock "

by N. Nakano , Research Institute for Polymers and Textiles, Agency of Industrial Science and Technology, MITI.

By the fatigue test of CFRP plates under heat and humidity cycles, the changes of thermal characteristics and flexural strength were observed. And its strength degradation of CFRP plates by superimposed thermal shock cycles on three point static bending state was tested. (1).

IV-4 " Effect of Space Environmental Conditions on Mechanical Properties of CFRP "

by K. Sonoda , Manufacturing Development Laboratory, Mitsubishi Electric Corporation.

The effect of space environmental conditions on mechanical properties of CFRP was examined by two conditions : i.e., electron-beam radiation test and thermal-vacuum test.

The electron-beam radiation test showed no change in the mechanical properties of CFRP 3 mm thick plates for the irradiation up to 5000 Mrads. However, some decrease in the flexural strength was observed in notched samples.

In the thermal- vacuum test, the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) decreased rapidly by degassing when the temperature exceeded 175°C. TML (Total Mass Loss) and CVCM (Collected Volatile Condensable Materials) increased accordingly in the same temperature range. (1).

Conclusion

The national R & D Project on Advanced Composite Materials for Future Industry has started in 1981. Now it is around half run.

Depending on the degree of difficulties of R & D of composites, some areas are getting good result and some areas are partly still remaining unsolved points. Among them, the results of areas which were considerably advanced were briefly introduced, based on the reference (1).

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